

Petru Maior
UNIVERSITY
OF
TÎRGU MUREŞ

FACULTY OF SCIENCES AND LETTERS

7TH EDITION

*THE INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE*

EUROPEAN INTEGRATION BETWEEN TRADITION AND MODERNITY

TÎRGU MUREŞ, 26-27 OCTOBER, 2017

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Lecturer Dumitru-Mircea Buda, PhD (*Tîrgu Mureş*, Romania)

CONFERENCE SCHEDULE

THURSDAY - 26 OCTOBER 2017

9⁰⁰ - 11⁰⁰ - Registration – Room R21

11⁰⁰ - 12³⁰ - Welcome and Opening – Aula Magna

12³⁰ - 13⁰⁰ – Coffee break

13⁰⁰ - 14³⁰ – Paper Presentations on Sections:

- ✓ Language and Discourse – Room A412
- ✓ Literature and Cultural Studies – Aula Magna
- ✓ History, Elites and Mentalities – Room R39
- ✓ Contemporary Political Challenges, European Communication and Context – Room R36

14³⁰ - 16⁰⁰ – Lunch

16⁰⁰ - 18³⁰ - Paper Presentations on Sections

19⁰⁰ - Gratulatory Dinner

The EITM 7 Conference is sponsored by:

**THE "ALPHA" ASSOCIATION FOR CULTURE, MULTIMEDIA
AND DEMOCRATIC EDUCATION – TÎRGU MUREŞ**

FRIDAY – 27 OCTOBER 2017

Sightseeing: cultural objectives in the Mureş county.

A WORD FROM THE ORGANIZERS

DEAR GUESTS,

The fundamental aim of the International Conference *European Integration between Tradition and Modernity – 7* is that of uniting, within topics related to *Human Studies*, emerging scholars and researchers from different fields of relevance for the contemporary society, a society that is supposed to secure its future not only on the economic and ecological level, but also on the spiritual one. The *cultural discourse, literature, history, the study of Political sciences*, as well as the *theories related to communication, language and discourse* are now redimensioned through a fundamental structural progress, so that the social end-results of education and research become extremely important. It is a fact that in our postmodern times, we live in a society of knowledge, from which we benefit directly in our everyday life, but to the risks and dangers of which we are at the same time exposed. *Non scholae sed vitae discimus* (*We do not learn for the school, but for life*) becomes a creed that every academic institution has to put into practice by means of its activities. It is essential that the path between education and research is very short, especially in academic systems. Research generates new knowledge, creates a favourable

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atmosphere for change, and provides people with information and data which help them to become aware of the mysteries of the universe and to make the most of their activity in all fields of knowledge. In this fascinating century, to the noble mission of educating the younger generations we must also add the fruit of the efforts in research, materialized in interesting works and papers, together with ideas generated by the creative ability which ennobles the personality of the academic.

We therefore hope that this scientific event will take place under the most favourable auspices and that it will represent a remarkable starting point for further evolution and development in the field of knowledge. Let this international conference provide a good opportunity for us to gain and transfer knowledge, to generate new theories in the world of science – essential aspirations of any contemporary research.

Co-Presidents of the EITM – 7 Conference

Prof. Iulian Boldea, PhD
Prof. Cornel Sigmirean, PhD
Assoc. Prof. Giordano Altarozzi, PhD

THURSDAY – 26 OCTOBER 2017

LANGUAGE AND DISCOURSE – Room: A412

Moderators:

Assoc. Prof. Doina Butiurca,
”Sapientia” University of Tîrgu Mureş;
Assoc Prof. Luminița Chiorean, PhD,
”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş

1. Doina Butiurca, Assoc. Prof., PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *NANOTECHNOLOGY TERMINOLOGY WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF THE SPECIALIZED LANGUAGES OF TRADITIONAL SCIENCES*
2. Loredana Bloju, Assoc. Prof., PhD, University of Piteşti, *ORTHOGRAPHY AND PUNCTUATION - A NECESSITY AND A CHALLENGE OF THE PRIMARY SCHOOL EDUCATION*
3. Daniela Dunca, Assoc. Prof., PhD, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca - Baia Mare Northern University Center, *RHETORIC IN POLITICS AND THE FORMS OF COMMUNICATIONAL AGREEMENT*
4. Luminița Chiorean, Assoc. Prof., PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *THE INTERPRETATION OF THE LITERARY TEXT FROM THE PERSPECTIOF HISTORICAL CULTUREMES.*
5. Bianca-Oana Han, Assoc. Prof., PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *ON ASPECTS REGARDING THE CULTURAL DIMENSION IN TRANSLATION*
6. Eva Monica Szekely, Assoc. Prof., PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *MULTIMODAL DISCOURSE IN THE NEW CURRICULA OF ROMANIAN LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE*

7. Simona Staicu, Lecturer, PhD, Victor Babeş University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Cluj-Napoca.
8. Maria Aldea, Senior Lecturer, PhD, "Babeş-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, *NAMES OF REPTILES, AMPHIBIANS AND INVERTEBRATES IN THE LEXICON OF BUDA (1825)*
9. Andreea Năznean, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *THE IMPORTANCE OF USING THE MOTHER TONGUE IN TEACHING TECHNICAL ENGLISH*
10. Maria-Laura Rus, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *PHONETIC PHENOMENA DUE TO COARTICULATION IN DACOROMANIAN DIALECT*
11. Corina Bozedeau, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *LA TRADUCTION DU TEXTE DRAMATIQUE*
12. Nicoleta Aurelia Marcu, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN DESIGNING LEGAL ENGLISH TEACHING MATERIALS*
13. Daniela Dălălaşu, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *THE IMPLICATIONS OF USING CORPUS-ANALYSIS PROGRAMS FOR STUDYING THE TRANSLATION OF CONCEPTUAL METAPHORS IN ECONOMIC AND FINANCIAL PRESS ARTICLES TRANSLATED FROM ENGLISH INTO ROMANIAN*

THURSDAY – 18 MAY 2017

LITERATURE AND CULTURAL STUDIES – Aula Magna

Moderators:

Prof. Iulian Boldea, PhD,

”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş;

Lecturer Dumitru-Mircea Buda, PhD,

”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş;

1. Mircea A. Diaconu, Prof., PhD, Ştefan cel Mare University of Suceava, *TRUTH, FICTION AND IDEOLOGY IN THE RECONSTRUCTION OF HISTORY. THE CASE OF MARIN MINCU*
2. Virgil Podoabă, Prof. PhD, ”Transilvania” University of Braşov, *THE NEW ORPHEUS*
3. Iulian Boldea, Prof., PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *ETHICS AND CONFESSION. WRITERS IN FRONT OF THE MIRROR*
4. Dorin Ştefănescu, Prof. PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *ION VINEA AND THE EPIPHANY OF THE VISIBLE*
5. Simona Antofi, Prof. PhD, ”Dunărea de Jos” University of Galaţi, *WORLD LITERATURE AND LITERATURE AS A WORLD IN MATEI CĂLINESCU’S UNPUBLISHED JOURNAL TOWARDS ROMANIA (2000-2002)*
6. Simona Antofi, Prof., PhD, ”Dunărea de Jos” University of Galaţi, *ON ‘THE WORLD REPUBLIC OF LETTERS’ – AN INTRIGUING CONCEPT AND RELEVANT CONTEMPORARY STUDY*

7. Smaranda Ștefanovici, Assoc. Prof., PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureș, *SOCIAL IDENTITY IN JOJO MOYES'S ME BEFORE YOU*
8. Carmen Simona Opreșor, Assoc. Prof., PhD, "Lucian Blaga" University of Sibiu, *EMIL CIORAN – TREATISE OF DECOMPOSITION – A DISCOURSE UPON THE CONTINUOUS END*
9. Virgil Borcan, Lecturer, PhD, "Transilvania" University of Brașov, *PROMETHEUS AND HIS ACOLYTES*
10. Corina Lirca, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureș, *THE CHARACTER OF KISWANA BROWNE IN THE DYNAMICS OF THE WOMEN OF BREWSTER PLACE BY GLORIA NAYLOR*
11. Corina Lirca, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureș, *INTERTEXTUALITY AS A NARRATIVE DEVICE IN GLORIA NAYLOR'S THE WOMEN OF BREWSTER PLACE*
12. Cristina Nicolae, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureș, *LIFE REDIRECTED. CASE-STUDY: DOWNSHIFTING*
13. Simona Staicu, Lecturer, PhD, Victor Babeș University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Timișoara, *MEDICAL CONSTRUCTIONS. DIVERSITY AND STRUCTURE*
14. Dumitru-Mircea Buda, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureș, *MONICA LOVINESCU AND VIRGIL IERUNCA, LOOKED BACK FROM NOWADAYS ROMANIA*
15. Andreea Pop, PhD, "Babeș-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, *TRACES OF SELFHOOD. THE SEMIOTICS OF BODY WASTE IN SOME POSTMODERN FRANCOPHONE AND ANGLOPHONE NOVELS*
16. Andreea Pop, PhD, "Babeș-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, *FROM ANNUNCIATION TO RESURRECTION: A VISUAL PRAGMATICS OF THE SUBLIME BODY*

17. Nicoleta Marinescu, PhD Student, "Babeş-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, *DOUBLES AND ICONS: THE ART OF THE MISE EN ABYME IN VLADIMIR NABOKOV'S ULTIMA THULE AND GORGE LUIS BORGES'S THLON, UQBAR, ORBIS TERTIUS*
18. Cristina Raica, PhD Student, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *THE GASTRONOMIC IMAGINARY IN THE POEMS OF EMIL BRUMARU*
19. Marian Suciu, PhD Student, "Babeş-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, *MASCULINE IDENTITY IN CHINESE AMERICAN LITERATURE AND HISTORY*
20. Olga Grădinaru, PhD, "Babeş-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, Independent Researcher, *SVETLANA ALEXIEVICH AND DISSONANT PERSPECTIVE ON WORLD WAR II*
21. Zaban Marta, PhD, Babeş-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, *CONCEPTS OF DRAMATIC CRITICISM IN HUNGARIAN LITERATURE IN THE MIDDLE OF THE 19TH CENTURY*
22. Aurora Gheorghita, PhD Student, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *The sources of Liviu Rusu's aesthetics*
23. Mirela Iulia Cioloca, PhD Student, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *ANALYSIS OF TWO INTERWAR PUBLICATIONS: „DARUL VREMII“ AND „GÂND ROMÂNESC“*
24. Iulia Luca, PhD Student, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *AUTOBIOGRAPHY AND DREAM IN EUGEN IONESCU'S WORK*
25. Oana Lucia Csatlos (Sava), PhD Student, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *THE MYTH OF LABYRINTH IN THE WORKS OF MIRCEA ELIADE*

THURSDAY – 18 MAY 2017

HISTORY, ELITES AND MENTALITIES – Room: R39

Moderators:

Prof. Cornel Sigmirean, PhD

”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş

Assoc. Prof. Giordano Altarozzi, PhD

”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş

1. Mihaela Grancea, Prof., PhD, ”Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *FUNCTIONALITY AND FINALITY OF HISTORICAL EVENT’S PHOTOGRAPHY*
2. Prof. Cornel Sigmirean, PhD and Lecturer Corneliu-Cezar Sigmirean, PhD - ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *WAR PROPAGANDA IN THE RELIGIOS PRESS : THE ”UNIREA” JOURNAL FROM BLAJ*
3. Dumitru-Cătălin Rogojanu, Scientific Researcher III, PhD, The Museum of Dacian and Roman Civilisation, Deva, *THE 100 YEARS CELEBRATION OF THE GREAT UNION: COMMEMORATION, MEMORY, HISTORY*
4. Giordano Altarozzi, Assoc. Prof., PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *BETWEEN HISTORIC MEMORY AND PROPAGANDA. THE BATTLE OF LEPANTO IN VISUAL ARTS*
5. Veronica Gaspar, Assoc. Prof., PhD, National University of Music, Bucharest, *CULTURAL TIME AND SPACE IN THE ‘EUROPE OF CULTURES’*
6. Veronica Gaspar, Assoc. Prof., PhD, National University of Music, Bucharest, *FROM EUROCENTRISM TILL EURO-*

PHOBIA: PERCEPTION AND ANALYSIS IN INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

7. Maria Tătar-Dan, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *HISTORY AND NATION: LANDMARK EVENTS THAT SHAPED ROMANIAN NATIONAL IDENTITY. CASE STUDY: THE REVOLUTION OF 1848*
8. Fabian Istvan, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *'DECORA' AND 'PERTINACIA'? PERCEPTIONS TOWARD DISFIGURED SOLDIERS IN THE ROMAN WORLD*
9. Georgeta Fodor, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *"THE UNWOMANLY FACE OF WAR": THE GREAT WAR THROUGH THE EYES OF ROMANIAN WOMEN FROM TRANSYLVANIA*
10. Alessandro Vagnini, Lecturer, PhD, Sapienza University of Rome (Italy), *SMALL POWERS AT THE PARIS PEACE CONFERENCE. BRĂTIANU AND THE FAILED ATTEMPT FOR A COMMON STRATEGY*
11. Rozalia Benedek, Assist., PhD, "Babeş-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, *AGRARIAN TRADITIONS AND MODERNIZATION IN DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL SĂLAJ*
12. Roberto Sciarrone, Research fellow, PhD, Sapienza University (Rome), *1917, THE OBER OST AND THE BACKGROUND OF THE LITHUANIAN INDEPENDENCE*
13. Iulia-Alexandra Oprea, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *TURKEY'S ALEVIS: BETWEEN EXCLUSION AND SUNNIFICATION*
14. Augusta-Manuela Lateş, PhD Student, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *MANIPULATION AND PROPAGANDA IN TELEVISION DURING THE COLD WAR*
15. Monica Crăciuneanu, PhD Student, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *GEMSTONES IN LATE RENAISSANCE: FROM ANCIENT MYTHS TO CHRISTIAN SYMBOLS REFLECTED IN ADORNMENTS*

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16. Adrian Gheorghe Standavid, PhD Student, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *TRANSYLVANIAN ELITES AND COLLECTIVE MENTALITY*
17. Elena Păduraru, Valahia University of Târgovişte, *THE ECONOMY OF PLOIEŞTI IN 1938*
18. Mihai Fulger, PhD Student, The Center for Excellence in the Study of Image, University of Bucharest, *AESTHETIC CANON VS. POPULAR CANON IN COMMUNIST ROMANIA'S FILM CULTURE*

THURSDAY – 18 MAY 2017

***CONTEMPORARY POLITICAL CHALLENGES,
EUROPEAN COMMUNICATION AND CONTEXT -
Room: R36***

Moderators:

Lecturer Mihaela Boloş, PhD,

”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş

Lecturer Eugeniu Nistor, PhD,

”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş

1. Lucreția Dogaru, Prof., PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *THE CONSEQUENCES OF THE INTERFERENCE BETWEEN NATIONAL LAW AND EUROPEAN LAW*
2. Lucreția Dogaru, Prof., PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *ASPECTS OF THE EUROPEAN UNION’S ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY*
3. Simion Costea, Assoc. Prof., PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *THE 20 DELIVERABLES OF THE EU’S EASTERN PARTNERSHIP BY 2020. AN EARLY ANALYSIS OF THIS EU’S WORK PLAN*
4. Eugeniu Nistor, Lecturer, PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *COMMUNICATION PROCESSES IN THE PUBLIC SPACE*
5. Mihaela Boloş, Lecturer, PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *EUROPEAN VS. NATIONAL BRAND*
6. Liviu Boar, PhD, Assoc. Lecturer, PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş, *RESERVED TITLE*
7. Lecturer Corneliu-Cezar Sigmirean, PhD, ”Petru Maior” University of Tîrgu Mureş *URBAN IDENTITIES: THE BRAND OF THE CITY OF TÎRGU MUREŞ*

8. Lucian Săcălean, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *POLITICAL CHALLENGES IN THE NEW EUROPEAN CONTEXT*
9. Lucian Săcălean, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş and Boglarka Gall, MA Student, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *POLITICAL PARTICIPATION AND POLITICAL CHANGE IN EUROPE*
10. Marius Paşcan, Lecturer, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *INTERPERSONAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMUNICATION. FUNDAMENTAL TRANSFORMATIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF THE NEW COMMUNICATION AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES*
11. Marius-Dumitru Crăciun, PhD, "Petru Maior" University of Tîrgu Mureş, *A CHANGE IN STRATEGIC AND GEOPOLITICAL PARADIGM IN ROMANIA'S AREA OF INTEREST*
12. Maria Costea, PhD, "Ghe. Şincai" Institute for Social Sciences and Humanities of the Romanian Academy, *RUSSIA'S STRATEGIC COMMUNICATION AND ITS IMPACT IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA, COMPARED TO THE EU'S EFFORTS*
13. Nelu-Cristian Moldovan, PhD, University of Bucharest, *ROMANIA IN 2017 – 10 YEARS AFTER THE EU ACCESSION AND 2 YEARS BEFORE TAKING OVER THE FIRST PRESIDENCY OF THE EU COUNCIL*
14. Victor Ioan Chira, PhD, Vasile Lucaciu National College, Baia Mare, *FROM EXPRESSION TO SIGNIFICANCE IN TODAY'S EUROPE*
15. Doru-Constantin Tocilă, PhD, Ministry of National Defense, Bucharest, *GEOPOLITICAL TRENDS AND ROLE OF NATO'S MILITARY SOFT POWER IN EASTERN EUROPE'S NEIGHBORHOOD*
16. Bukfeyes-Rakossy Zsombor, MA Student, "Babeş-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, *REALITIES AND PERSPECTIVES OF EUROPEAN STRUCTURAL AND INVESTMENT FUNDS SIMPLIFICATION*

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